

1 An Innovative Extraction Methodology of Active
2 Deformation Areas Based on Sentinel-1 SAR Dataset:
3 the Catalonia case study

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15 **Abstract:** Persistent Scatterer interferometry (PSI) has been proved to be an advanced
16 interferometric SAR (InSAR) technique used to measure and monitor terrain deformation. Two of
17 the critical problems with InSAR have been the effect of the refractive atmosphere and
18 decorrelation on the interferometric phases due to long spatial-temporal baseline. The low density
19 of Persistent Scatterers (PS) in non-urban areas affected by spatial-temporal decoherence more
20 seriously has inspired the development of alternative approaches. Sentinel-1 (S1) has improved
21 the data acquisition throughout, and compared to previous sensors, increased considerably the
22 differential interferometric SAR (DInSAR) and PSI deformation monitoring potential. This paper
23 describes an innovative methodology to process S1 SAR data. Different with PSI, its most original
24 part includes two key processing stages: high and low frequency splitting from wrapped phases,
25 prior to atmospheric filtering, and final direct integration to generate the complete deformation
26 with time series (TS) containing linear and nonlinear components. The proposed method has two
27 fundamental advantages compared with traditional PSI approach: the final monitoring results with
28 excellent coverage of coherent points and the generation of active maps even for the areas with

29 serious deformation in short term to break through the inherent limitation of PSI. The
30 effectiveness of the proposed tools is illustrated using a case study located in Catalonia (Spain).
31 This methodology has supposed a definitive step towards the implementation of DInSAR based
32 techniques to support decision makers against geohazards. In this work, the deformation
33 procedures happened in three different areas of the Catalonia (Spain) are presented and analyzed.
34 The maximum accumulated subsidence of over -60cm induced by mining activity can be detected
35 by proposed methodology with nice coverage from January 2017 to January 2019. These reported
36 cases illustrate how DInSAR based techniques can provide detailed terrain deformation for
37 geohazard activity with complex topographical conditions. The active deformation areas (ADA)
38 map can be generated in fast aimed at geohazard risk early warning and management.

39

40 **Keywords:** Persistent Scatterer Interferometry; frequency splitting; direct integration; terrain
41 deformation; risk management

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44 **1. Introduction**

45 This paper is focused on TS deformation extraction by using S1 data with great spatial coverage
46 and high resolution. In the last 30 years, the spaceborne DInSAR technique has received great
47 improvements since it was proposed with L-band Seasat SAR data at first in 1989 (Gabriel et al.
48 1989). The advanced approach needs large sets of SAR Images is the so-called PSI technique
49 published by Ferretti and co-authors (Ferretti et al. 2001). During last two decades, a wide number
50 of data processing and analysis tools and methods are generated in this period. An excellent
51 review of Spaceborne DInSAR techniques can be found in (Crosetto et al. 2016) which include the
52 classical standard DInSAR, PSI analysis over small areas, full PSI with linear deformation model
53 and with free deformation model, while a specific application of DInSAR for geohazard mapping
54 is presented in (Barra et al. 2017).

55 Generally, PSI is a powerful radar based remote sensing technique able to monitor
56 displacements of the Earth's surface (Núria et al. 2018). Among the pioneering techniques, PSI
57 can improve InSAR accuracy by exploiting the persistent scatterers with high spatial-temporal

58 stabilities, nevertheless, this significantly reduces the possibility of InSAR applications in rural
59 areas. The low PS density in non-urban areas has blocked the invention of complementary
60 techniques to PSI. To exploit partially decorrelating areas in TS analysis, all SAR images has been
61 utilized for the interferograms generation even if the baseline between these two acquisitions is
62 longer than the critical length. In this way, poor-quality interferograms with long spatial-temporal
63 baseline can be selected for PSI measurement and high-quality interferograms with short temporal
64 baseline may be discarded to guarantee the independence of atmospheric phase over time.
65 However, the classic PSI approach utilizes the linear deformation model to extract the
66 displacement phases. As a consequence, in the areas where displacements are characterized by
67 non-linear motion, there will be no PSs (K.Pawluszek-Filipiak, 2020) .

68 Although this advanced technique has experienced a continuous growth, it is important to
69 underline the DInSAR techniques are not universal. The two intrinsic limitations of DInSAR
70 techniques are less density of PS due to coherence loss for long-term deformation monitoring
71 (especially for non-urban area) and phase ambiguities estimation from the wrapped phase. Due to
72 the PS should be considered as stable with respect to a reference point, such as rocky outcrops or
73 hand-made artifacts, the number of them is very limited in mountain areas where always have
74 geohazard phenomenon (e.g., landslide, earthquake). Moreover, the wrapped phases are difficult
75 to estimate ambiguities exactly because the interferograms generated form SAR image pairs
76 include atmosphere, topography, deformation phases and so on (Crosetto et al. 2010) and the
77 phase unwrapping procedure is time costing due to the atmosphere turbulences not suitable to
78 recognize the geohazard quickly.

79 Having considered the limitation of PSI approach, a procedure for ADA extraction over wide
80 coverage containing coherent points with high density and temporal sampling (the minimum
81 revisiting cycle is six days) for the geohazard management is designed elaborately and carried out
82 in this study. A dataset of C-band S1 images over the Catalonia (Spain) were employed for
83 monitoring measurement, it is worth mentioning the procedures of TS deformation were
84 investigated well by the proposed method based on S1 acquisitions with short spatial-temporal
85 baselines in our work.

86 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed workflow and the tools for

87 the TS deformation extraction. The study area input dataset and the main results of the application
 88 of the methodology to the test areas are shown in Section 3 and discussed in Section 4. Finally,
 89 Section 5 presents the main conclusions.

90

91 **2. Methodology**

92 In this section, the processing chain to derive the TS deformation estimation and ADA maps
 93 extraction is illustrated in detail. The proposed procedure can be applied to the data acquired by
 94 any satellite SAR sensor. However, it provides the best performances with the S1 characteristic
 95 due to its high spatial coverage and temporal resolution.

96 According to InSAR principle and frequency spectrum analysis (P. Olea et al.2020; Qiu Z et al.
 97 2020), the interferometric phases can be divided into two parts: High Frequency (HF) and Low
 98 Frequency (LF). Since the systematic errors caused by the DEM or orbit errors could be corrected
 99 by calibration , these errors can be ignored in this study. Hence, the detailed model can be
 100 described as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi &= \varphi_{def} + \varphi_{atmo} + \varphi_{noi} = \Phi_{high} + \Phi_{low} \\
 &= (\varphi_{def_main} + \varphi_{noi})_{high} + (\varphi_{def_res} + \varphi_{atmo})_{low}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

102 Where φ_{def} is the deformation phase, φ_{atm} is atmospheric phase and φ_{noi} is noise phase,
 103 φ_{def_main} is the main part of the deformation phase, and φ_{def_res} represents the residual
 104 deformation phase. The noise and atmospheric signals in the interferogram are located at high and
 105 low frequency respectively, while the deformation signal exists in the entire frequency spectrum,
 106 the deformation phase can be extracted by effective frequency division processing (Daniel R et al.,
 107 2013; Bru G et al., 2017). In particular, for this research, the interferograms have been generated
 108 using an approach of Persistent Scatter Interferometry chain of the Geomatics (PSIG) Division of
 109 CTTC described in (Devanry et al. 2014). The general scheme of the procedure, shown as a
 110 flowchart in Figure 1, can be divided in several main blocks.

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Figure 1. Flow chart of the proposed procedure

2.1 Interferograms network Generation

To generate interferograms network with short spatial-temporal baseline, several steps should have been done before. This analysis provides key inputs for the network like the minimum temporal baseline to be used since the deformation detection quality could be guaranteed with high coherence. Therefore, the data with same temporal baseline (such as 6 or 12 days) are collected for the interferograms network generation. After extraction from bursts and swaths of S1 dataset, the key step is the image co-registration, which could be very accurate for interferometric phase by means of auxiliary Digital Elevation Model (DEM) before the interferograms generation. After the step of co-registration, the interferograms between the pairs can be created for next steps.

2.2 High and Low frequency splitting and direct integration

- (1) High and Low frequency splitting: Since an interferogram consists of much complex phase information such as deformation, atmosphere and noise. etc., it is very difficult to extract the deformation information from wrapped phases directly and correctly. An innovative approach has been proposed here is to split the consecutive interferograms into two parts: high and low frequency. The noise and displacement phase are treated as HF segment mainly which is useful to accomplish our detection test, and atmospheric phase as LF segment is worthless for our goal, but the residual deformed phases still exist in LF. A proper and empirical threshold is adopted in this step to extract the deformation from the interferograms mainly. However, different thresholds should be evaluated in order to acquire the best separation effect. For example, in the Catalonia test site, only the pixels

134 with cut off threshold higher than 40 have been selected as HF segment by Butterworth
 135 band-pass filtering.
 136

$$|H_a(j\Omega)| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Omega}{\Omega_c}\right)^{2N}}} \quad (2)$$

137 In the above formula, Ω denotes the frequency, Ω_c is the cut-off frequency, N is the
 138 order. The LF band phase Φ_{low} dominated by atmospheric phase is separated from the
 139 interferogram, and then the HF band phase dominated by deformation phase is separated
 140 from the interferogram by conjugation operation, that is $\Phi_{high} = \Phi - \Phi_{low}$; the TS
 141 interferometric phase sequences corresponding to HF and LF are $\Phi_{high}^{(k)}$ and
 142 $\Phi_{low}^{(k)} \quad \forall k \in (1, 2, \dots, N-1)$ respectively, as shown in Figure 2. After HF and LF
 143 separation, the Goldstein filter is utilized to adaptively denoise the interferogram to
 144 remove the residual noise phase φ_{noi} in the HF phase.

146 Figure 2. Schematic diagram of high and low frequency band separation

147 (2) 2D phase unwrapping: Actually, this is a two-step spatial-temporal **phase unwrapping**
 148 **approach** (Crosetto, M et al, 2007). The phase unwrapping is performed twice in the
 149 procedure we proposed here: (i) prior to atmospheric filtering and (ii) during TS
 150 deformation generation. In the following, we treat separately these two stages which is a
 151 data quality control **step**. The first stage, which is prior to the atmospheric filtering, can
 152 generate the quality index for each pixel in the images. After HF and LF splitting, we start

153 with a spatial phase unwrapping (2D) performed over the selected set of points and for
 154 high and low interferograms separately. For each pixel, the main output is the evolution of
 155 the phases with respect to a reference image for each interferogram. The second stage,
 156 which is used to generate the TS deformation, can generate the quality index for each
 157 image of a given TS deformation. The quality indices are defined by the ratio (Cor_%)
 158 between the number of residuals and the total number of interferogram or image for data
 159 quality control, if this ratio is above 40%, all the pixels or images are labelled as “not
 160 Good” should be discarded form dataset in the subsequent processing steps. Therefore, the
 161 2+1D phase unwrapping can be employed as an analysis tool to guarantee the quality of
 162 pixels and interferograms for the TS deformation. In particular, it refers to the so-called
 163 2+1D phase unwrapping described in (Devanry et al. 2014).

164 (3) Direct integration for high and low frequency segment: This procedure can be used to
 165 correct the unwrapping errors. A pixel wise processing is performed in this step, which
 166 analyses over unwrapped interferometric phases with time series. By an iterative process,
 167 exploiting the Single Value Decomposition (SVD) least squares method and adopting an
 168 outlier rejection strategy, the matrix used for SVD is built by so-called residuals $R =$
 169 $\Delta\varphi - (\varphi_M - \varphi_S)$ associated with observations of unwrapped interferometric phases. This
 170 procedure determines the phases values associated with each SAR image, starting from a
 171 stack of interferograms. The high and low frequency combined phase over time is
 172 estimated accumulatively for each point as follows:

$$173 \quad \begin{cases} \varphi_i = \varphi_{i-1} + \Delta\varphi_{i(i-1)} & i = 1 \div N \\ \varphi_0 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

174 Where φ_i the accumulated phase at the acquisition is time i , and $\Delta\varphi_{i(i-1)}$ is the interferometric
 175 phase between the images i and $i-1$.

176 2.3 Active Deformation Areas (ADA) Extraction

177 The main goal of this block is to discover TS deformation of the active areas from interferograms
 178 fast and correctly, which is very meaningful for Geo-hazard detection and early warning. In this
 179 section, the procedure to detect the active deformation area from interferograms directly without
 180 any complex and time-consuming analysis is described. The automatic ADA detection strategy
 181 proposed in this article is a robust procedure performed using a set of spatial-temporal filters. In
 182 other words, the threshold parameter used just for the S1 should be changed to suit for other SAR

183 sensors. The full procedure consists in the following steps (Figure 3):

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185 Figure 3. Flow chart of ADA extraction

186 (1) HF&LF combination: From previous analysis of HF and LF splitting, the most parts of
 187 deformation phase are persisted in the HF segment. However, the rest still is contained in
 188 the LF segment. Then, these two parts of deformation should be combined for each PS
 189 pixel.

190 (2) 1D phase unwrapping: This is the second step for 2+1D phase unwrapping to check the
 191 phase unwrapping consistency done by point wise, exploiting the temporal component of
 192 SAR images stack. It is based on an iterative least square (LS) method and the analysis of
 193 the LS residuals at each iteration in order to correct the “phase jump”.

194 (3) Atmospheric phase estimation and reduction: The APS is estimated using spatial-temporal
 195 filters. The main input is the temporal evolution of the phases (TEP) estimated in the
 196 previous step. The estimated APS is removed from the TEP. The remaining phases are then
 197 transformed into deformations, obtaining the final TS deformation.

198 (4) ADA extraction: This is the last of the ADA extraction block after geocoding. It consists of
 199 nonlinear TS deformation without any temporal filtering, i.e., regression line estimation. The
 200 used method is a valid tool for the character analysis of the deformation phenomena such as

201 landslide, settlements and so on.

202 The final output of these blocks above is an ADA maps including, for each point, the
203 accumulated TS deformation along the satellite LOS direction at each acquisition time. The active
204 deformation area could be recognized from the geocoded outputs finally.

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206 **3 Catalonia Study Results**

207 In this section, several results obtained from the new strategy proposed in this article are presented
208 and discussed. The explained procedure has been applied to the Catalonia area in Spain, and there
209 are different types of geo-disasters such as urban settlement, mining subsidence and mountains
210 landslide or rockslide happened in this study area.

211 *3.1 Study Area*

212 These results were derived from S1 SAR images over Catalonia which is an autonomous
213 community of Spain consisting of four provinces: Barcelona, Girona, Lleida, and Tarragona.

214 Catalonia has a marked geographical diversity, considering the relatively small size of its
215 territory (Figure 4). The geography is conditioned by the Mediterranean coast, with 580
216 kilometers (360 miles) of coastline, and large relief units of the Pyrenees to the north. The Catalan
217 territory can be divided into three main geomorphologic units:

218 (1) The Pyrenees: mountainous formation that connects the Iberian Peninsula with the European
219 continental territory, and located in the north of Catalonia;

220 (2) The Catalan Coastal mountain ranges or the Catalan Mediterranean System: an alternating
221 elevations and planes parallel to the Mediterranean coast;

222 (3) The Catalan Central Depression: structural unit which forms the eastern sector of the Valley
223 of the Ebro.

Figure 4. Physical map of study area (the red dotted line) in Catalonia

3.2 Dataset Description

The study area Catalonia is covered by a single S1 frame. In particular, two swaths and 7 bursts have been processed for monitoring measurement. The main characteristics of the processed dataset are presented in Table 1. S1 is a constellation composed of two twin satellites acquiring images at C-band (central frequency 5.4 GHz and wavelength 5.6 cm) which grants a 6-days revisiting cycle and 12-days for single satellite. The used SAR dataset consists of 111 S1 Wide Swath images spanning around two years period, with the first acquisition time in January 2017 and last one in January 2019. All the images from twin S1 satellites have been collected for measurement in this study, and the minimum temporal gap is 6 days, while the maximum is 12 days which is defined by the image available situation. Figure 5 shows all the acquisition times of the processed images and perpendicular baselines of interferograms.

As explained in the introduction, the aim of this paper is to generate the TS deformation maps for Catalonia because the deformation procedure is quite useful and important for the geohazard analysis. One interferometric network was designed with the minimal temporal baseline (6 days or 12 days due to the data downloading failure) to guarantee the coherences between these pairs

241 shown in the Figure 5, which is the key point for interferograms generation with good quality.

242 The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM provided by NASA has been utilized in
243 coregistration and geocoding procedures to provide the interferometric products in this work
244 (Blanco et al. 2012).

245 **Table 1** Main characteristics of the processed data

Name	Value
Satellite	Sentinel-1A
Acquisition mode	Wide Swath
Minimum revisit period (days)	6
Wavelength (λ) (cm)	5.55
Polarization	VV
Full resolution (azimuth/range) (m)	14/4
Multi-look 1×5 resolution (azimuth/range) (m)	14/20
Multi-look 2×10 resolution (azimuth/range) (m)	28/40
Orbit	Descending
Incidence angle of the area of interest	$36.47^\circ \sim 41.85^\circ$
Period	January 2017~ January 2019

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Figure 5. The time-baseline plot of the processed interferograms

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3.1 Active Deformation results

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Figure 6. Footprint of the processed amplitude image and area of interest. The area is covered by 2

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sub-swaths and 7 bursts

255 The monitoring results of this study concern a large part of Catalonia, see Figure 6. The covered
256 area is approximately 19,000 km². 111 images have been processed by proposed method, the most
257 part of interferograms has been affected by serious decorrelation and noise with the mean
258 coherence less than 0.25(the threshold of PS candidates for PSI approach), see Figure 7(a), due to
259 the vegetation coverage and topography. However, the active deformation results with excellent
260 coverage could be generated using the proposed methodology, even for the active areas with large
261 scale displacement in short time, such as mining area.

262 To analysis these deformation results in deep, some examples of these generated results over
263 Catalonia are illustrated in Figure 7(b). Compared with results from traditional PSI techniques
264 (Devanry et al. 2019), more than 5 million coherent points could be extracted for deformation
265 monitoring with greater coverage which are valuable for civil risk evaluation and management.
266 The accumulated deformation maps from some areas are shown along with a sample of the
267 retrieved temporal deformation of a selected point among them. Three main deformation generator
268 mechanisms have been identified at the affected areas in Catalonia:

- 269 (1) Underground mining activities are detected using the proposed method in intense ADA
270 (towns of Sria, Cardona and Sallent among others) with great temporal serious
271 accumulated settlements in Figure 8 and 9.
- 272 (2) Heavy surface load in the Barcelona Port and Airport whose subsidence has already been
273 more than 10cm form January 2017 to January 2019. However, the dam nearby estuary of
274 the El Llobregat River has raised up more than 12cm in Figure 10 and 11.
- 275 (3) Intense water extraction is well recognized in some urban areas, most part of Igualada city
276 is very stable, but there is a few subsidence in the downtown of this city might cause by
277 water extraction or urban construction in Figure 12 and 13.

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Figure 7. Mean coherence map (a) and accumulated deformation map (b) of study area. Three examples of deformation results will be presented (red circle)

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Figure 8. Active deformation map of area A revealing a surface subsidence (over -60 cm) caused by

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mining activities during observation period

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Figure 9. Four points of deformation results with time series located in the area A shown in Figure 8

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(see yellow dots)

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Figure 10. Active deformation map of area B (Barcelona Ports). P1 and P2 have surface subsidence

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(-2~ -6 cm) due to surface loading during observation period, P3 has a lifting deformation (over 5 cm)

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caused by the sedimentation

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Figure 11. Three points of deformation results with time series located in the area B shown in Figure 10

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(yellow dots)

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301

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Figure

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e 12. Active deformation map of area C (Igalada). P1 and P2 are all very stable during observation

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period, but P3 has a settlement (-13 cm) caused by the water extraction

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Figure 13. Three points of deformation results with time series located in the area C shown in Figure 12

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(black circle)

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310 **4 Discussion**

311 The methodology proposed in this work (Section 2) has been employed for the semi-automatic
312 identification and pre-screening of deformational processes, and it was applied in the three case
313 studies and the results are presented in the third section using S1 datasets and ancillary data
314 (Section 3.2). The discussion is described in this section.

315 In this section, some key aspects, as well as the strengths and limitations of the presented
316 methodology are commented. The presented methodology is aimed at generating active
317 deformation maps with TS over wide areas, using the S1 images. The main challenge is to
318 generate rapidly and semi-automatically a product to be easily exploited in the geohazard
319 management by the Civil Protections and the Geological Surveys (P. Olea et al.2020).

320 The main advantage of the proposed method is the possibility of semi-automatically generating
321 active deformation maps with TS to reveal the subsidence procedure for wide areas and break the
322 maximum deformation detection ability of InSAR approach based on S1 datasets (Devanthery et
323 al. 2019). The output of the methodology is the TS deformation map which localizes only the most
324 important detected active areas, unlike the conventional output of velocity map, which can contain
325 all information of the interferometric phases without filtering and fitting process. The management
326 and administration of the civil safety and the infrastructures can receive the support from this
327 information of particular interests.

328 Furthermore, compared with other types of satellites, the better performances of the proposed
329 methodology could be obtained using S1 satellite data with short revisit time of the S1, varying
330 6-12 days and allowing a wide area monitoring.

331 The methodology suffers the same inherent limitation of InSAR approach and SAR satellite
332 data (Qiu et al. 2019; Yue et al. 2016). Apart from the theoretical drawback like acquisition
333 geometry and displacement limitation, there are two other aspects that spatially influence the
334 possibility of detecting movements: the frequency splitting process and the lack of noisy phase
335 elimination.

336

337 **5 Conclusions**

338 In this paper a regional operational project in Catalonia (Spain) has been described with the

339 objective to monitor surface deformation employing an Innovative Methodology and evaluate its
340 geohazard safety for civil protection over wide areas (Tang et al. 2015; Bouali et al. 2016;
341 Barhoux et al. 2014). DInSAR has proven to be an excellent tool for identifying affected areas at
342 wide spatial scale. The aim of this project is to extract the deformation areas from the SAR
343 satellite datasets in simple and fast way, specifically by the Civil Protection administrations in
344 order to discover and avoid the risk of geohazard in time. The outputs of the methodology are the
345 Deformation Areas Map (DAM) and the TS deformation, not only when evaluating the results but
346 also to improve the PS-DInSAR processing strategy with an excellent coverage and point's
347 density.

348 All the main steps of the methodology have been explained in this article, starting from the PSC
349 selection, the high and low frequency split and integration of high and low parts to generate the
350 DAM and the TS analysis of interesting PS points. The application and the results of the
351 methodology over mining and ports areas in the Catalonia (Spain) have been presented and
352 discussed. This innovative methodology improves the coverage and TS estimation of PS points
353 greatly, yields a much better characterization of the deformation phenomena. The systematic
354 integration of the results exhibits the regional scale monitoring potentialities of the proposed
355 methodology, and the detailed TS analysis allows now and, in the future, a better understanding
356 and quantification of the triggering mechanisms for geohazard evaluation purposes. Moreover, it
357 is worthy to investigate and explore the real physical meaning of the threshold of HF and LF
358 splitting adopted in our study. Considering the proper strategy suitable for other sensors and more
359 experiments need to be verified in our future research.

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367

368 **Author Contributions**

369 Zhiwei Qiu wrote the paper and was involved in the data processing and analysis; Michele Crosetto and Oriol

370 Monserrat (CTTC) contributed in the SAR data processing and analysis of the results; Vrinda Krishnakumar

371 provides the inputs analysis of Catalonia study test; Li Zhou modified the logical frame of this manuscript.

372

373 **Disclosure statement**

374 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

375

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